

PROSPECTS FOR ESTABLISHING A FREE TRADE ZONE BETWEEN THE EAEU AND INDIA

Givargizova L.

Institute for the Development of Integration Processes of the Russian Foreign Trade Academy of the Ministry of Economic Development of the Russian Federation (IDIP RFTA), analyst

ORCID ID – 0000-0003-4747-4169

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Abstract

At the current stage of development under sanctions pressure on the Russian economy, the expansion and strengthening of foreign economic relations with friendly countries and with countries participating in integration blocs and unions is of great importance. The issues of technical barriers, new solutions in the field of supply chains, customs co-operation and industry co-operation are becoming relevant. Taking into account the sanctions pressure on the Russian market from the beginning of 2022, it becomes necessary to expand trade and economic relations with friendly countries, focusing on those countries with which trade agreements have been signed, and the signing of a free trade zone agreement is also becoming a trend. India is one of Russia's important partner countries, both as an individual state and within the framework of co-operation between the EAEU and the BRICS bloc. Given the growing volume of mutual trade and the fact that a free trade area agreement between the EAEU and India has been under development since December 2016, we consider it necessary to analyze India's tariff policy. The article provides a statistical analysis of the Eurasian Economic Union's foreign trade turnover with India since 2016 (the year of the start of negotiations on the creation of a free trade zone); the dynamics of India's most-favoured-nation treatment; the applied ad valorem and specific rates of customs duties; India's trade agreements, as well as India's bound and applied tariffs on certain groups of goods and tariff quotas.

Keywords: India, Russia, Eurasian Economic Union, Free Trade Area, Most Favored Nation Regime, WTO, bound and applied tariffs, tariff quotas.

Introduction

In the 1960s and 1980s, the economic difficulties of developing countries made it necessary to consider integration as a tool to increase the levels of economic development. At the present stage of development, the processes continue, but they are no longer as spontaneous and dynamic as in the pre-pandemic period. Covid-19 can be regarded as the first stage of slowdown of integration processes, and the next stage can be considered the following geopolitical events, such as sanctions against Russia and disruption of supply chains, development of infrastructure projects, search for new markets and development of new supply chains. Given the new economic realities of Russia and their impact on the Eurasian Economic Union (hereinafter EAEU), it is necessary to analyse the trade and economic relations of the union. Given the new economic realities of Russia - sanctions, subsequently parallel imports, the EAEU member countries that provide the Russian market with parallel imports may also fall under sanctions [1]. There is a need to expand trade and economic relations with friendly countries, focusing on those states with which trade agreements have been signed and the main trading partners of the Eurasian Economic Union. India is an important trading partner, despite the fact that it ranks 13th according to foreign trade turnover statistics for 2021, but most of the countries ahead of India are those that have imposed sanctions against Russia, with the exception of China. Nevertheless, it is necessary to analyze and identify the potential of trade and economic relations between India and the EAEU, India's tariff policy, changes in the dynamics of the average most-favored-nation (MFN) rate applied. The study is based on the methodology of analysis and synthesis in the study of scientific sources, further reveal-

ing the relationship between trade and economic relations and the creation of a Free Trade Area (hereinafter FTA).

The method of induction, which is associated with the study of the level of development of tariff policy and tariff regulation, is also applicable to the entire study, which ultimately allows drawing general conclusions about the prospects for a FTA between the EAEU and India. The issues of customs and tariff policy with the EAEU countries, the prospects of a FTA with India were considered based on the works of the authors A. G. Cariappa, K. K. Acharya, Ch. A. Adhav, R. Sendhil, P. Ramasundaram, A. Kumar, S. Singh, G. P. Singh [2]; Cariappa, A.G.A., Kathayat, B., Karthiga, S., Sendhil, R. [3]; V. Gupta, D. Ivanov, Tsan-Ming Choi [4]; N. Sudha, S. Shree [5]; D. J. Kuenzel, R. R. Sharma [6]; M. Ghodsi [7]; E. Ornelas, P. Tovar [8]; J. Grüber, O. Reiter [9]; D. J. Kuenzel, R. R. Sharma [10]; C. Beverelli, R. Ticku [11] and based on the WTO statistics.

Trade cooperation between the EAEU and India

On December 6, 2016, the Supreme Eurasian Economic Council issued Decision No. 14 "On the start of negotiations with the Republic of India on a free trade zone". [12]. Technical consultations were held in 2018 and 2019 to agree on the format of the upcoming negotiations and the planned free trade agreement. The first round of negotiations was scheduled for March 2020, but was postponed to a later date due to the COVID-19 pandemic [13]. At this stage of development, the agreement on an FTA between the EAEU and India is under development. However, it is necessary to analyze the foreign trade turnover between the EAEU and India to understand the potential of the markets and the growth prospects of trade and economic relations.

India ranked 13th among foreign trade partners in 2021 according to statistics from the Eurasian Economic Commission [14], but all countries above 13th place are all those that have imposed sanctions against Russia, except China. Given the blocking of a huge number of markets, India and the EAEU are facing new prospects for the development of mutual trade and economic relations. Looking at 2016, given that it was the

starting year for the EAEU-India FTA negotiations, trade turnover has been growing each subsequent year (see Figure 1). There was a decline in 2020, due to supply chain blockages due to the pandemic, and there is a 31.7% or \$16.345 billion increase in 2021.

Figure 1 Increase in trade turnover between the EAEU and India compared to the previous period
Source: compiled and calculated by the author on the basis of EEC data [15]

India and the WTO

India has been a member of the WTO since January 1, 1995. Customs duties are regulated by the Customs Tariff Act, 1975 [16]. Import duty is levied on all goods imported into the country, including products for the needs of government agencies.

According to WTO data, the simple average applied MFN tariff in India has changed periodically

since WTO accession (see Figure 2). In recent years there has been an increase, which exports attribute to the "Make in India" initiative (launched on September 25, 2014) [17]. The first initiative aimed at the development of the country's manufacturing sector, including by protecting it from foreign competition.

Figure 2 The dynamics of the average MFN rate in India from 2015 to 2021
Source: compiled by the authors based on WTO iLibrary data [18]

India also applies export duties on 56 commodity items, both ad valorem and specific, including coffee - 2.2 thousand rupees per quintal, tea - 5 rupees per kg, sugar - 20%, mica - 40%, ilmenite - 30%, hides and skins - 60%, etc. [19].

India uses both ad valorem and nonad valorem tariff rates on imports. 91.2% of tariff lines have ad valorem duty rates, 725 tariff lines (6.1% of the total) are

subject to non-ad valorem rates: of these, 4 are subject to special rates (almonds in shell and husk, crude oil and crude oil products) and 721 tariff lines are subject to mixed duties. Mixed duties apply to textiles and clothing (714 tariff lines) and natural rubber products (7 lines). For the remaining 2.7% of goods, import customs duty rates do not apply [20]. (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Structure of India's customs tariff by types of duties

Source: compiled by the authors on the basis of data [20]

India bound 74.3% of its tariff lines. As in the case of applied MFN rates, most of the bound rates are ad valorem (92%); only textiles and garments are bound by mixed duties, and two lines (almonds in shell and husk) are bound by specific rates. India bound 100% of the tariff lines relating to agricultural products at rates ranging from 10% to 300%, and 71.7% of the tariffs applied to non-agricultural products. The latter are bound at lower tariff rates, ranging from 0 to 150%. The

highest bound rates are agreed for oilseeds, fats, oils and their products (300%), and animal products; dairy products; fruits, vegetables, plants; coffee, tea; grains and billets; sugar and confectionery; drinks and tobacco; cotton; other agricultural products; fish and fish products; chemicals (100%) [21].

India's average MFN tariff in 2021 was 18.3%, with a bound tariff of 50.8%. The weighted average applied tariff was 12.6%. (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 - India's tariff protection levels

Source: compiled by the authors on the basis of data [22]

According to the WTO, average tariff rates for all commodity items were increased in 2021 compared with 2015 (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Dynamics of change in tariffs for consumer goods (marked in the figure in the figures of the tariff rates of 2021)

Source: compiled by the authors based on WTO iLibrary data [18]

The highest MFN rates apply to the following commodity items (see Table 1):

1. Beverages and tobacco. The average MFN rate applied is 76.3%;
2. Coffee, tea - 56,5;
3. Oilseeds, oils and fats- 53.4%;
4. Sugar and confectionery - 51.5%;
5. Cereals and preparations - 37.3%;
6. Fruit, vegetables and plants - 33.6%.

The highest rates, about 328% apply in relation to the commodity item textiles. Duty of 150% applies to the following goods items: crops and preparations; beverages and tobacco, 125% in respect of the goods item vehicles, 120% - fruits, vegetables, plants; 119% - clothing; 100% - animal products; coffee and tea; oilseeds, oils and fats; sugar and confectionery products and chemicals (see Table 1).

Table 1

Related and applicable MFN rates of import customs tariffs in India by commodity group

Product Groups	Final bound duties			MFN applied duties			Imports	
	AVG	Duty-free in %	Max	AVG	Duty-free in %	Max	Share in %	Duty-free in %
Animal products	104.5	0	150	32.5	0	100	0.0	0
Dairy products	63.8	0	150	35.7	0	60	0.0	0
Fruit, vegetables, plants	101.2	0	150	33,6	0	120	1.4	0
Coffee, tea	133.1	0	150	56.3	0	100	0.1	0
Cereals & preparations	114.1	0	150	37.3	13.2	150	0.1	8.4
Oilseeds, fats & oils	165.1	0	300	53.4	0	100	3.2	0
Sugar and confectionery	126.2	0	150	51.5	0	100	0.2	0
Beverages & tobacco	120.4	0	150	76.3	0	150	0.2	0
Coton	110.0	0	150	26.0	0	30	0.1	0
Other agricultural products	105.6	0	150	29.0	7.4	70	0.5	0.8
Fish & fish products	135.7	0	150	30	0	30	0.1	0
Minerals & metals	38.3	0.4	55	11.8	0.1	40	32,7	0
Petroleum	-	-	-	9.2	0	10	16.6	0
Chemicals	39.6	0.1	150	10.3	0.2	100	13	0.2
Wood, paper, etc.	36.6	0	91	10.5	2.1	25	1.6	0.1
Textiles	27.3	0	85	25.5	0	328	1.3	0
Clothing	37.7	0	68	24.1	0	119	0.2	0
Leather, footwear, etc.	34.6	0	40	14.6	0	70	0.9	0

Product Groups	Final bound duties			MFN applied duties			Imports	
	AVG	Duty-free in %	Max	AVG	Duty-free in %	Max	Share in %	Duty-free in %
Non-electrical machinery	28.6	6.3	40	8.2	3.7	20	9.4	27.0
Electrical machinery	27.8	24.6	40	10.3	14.8	20	11.7	24.2
Transport equipment	35.7	0	40	31.1	0	125	3.8	0
Manufactures, n.e.s.	33.5	14.5	40	11.9	4.1	60	2.9	15.2

Source: compiled by the authors on the basis of data [22]

The Government of India decides annually whether to grant, either import tariff quotas or quantitative quotas. Import tariff quotas applied from October 14, 2021, to March 31, 2022, for crude soybean oil, edible soybean oil, crude palm oil, refined palm oil and any palm oil, unrefined sunflower oil, edible sunflower oil (see Table 2) [23]. Quantitative quotas are in effect from May 25, 2022 to March 31, 2024 [24].

Table 2

Import tariff within the quota and above it

№	Commodity Nomenclature of FEA	Goods item	Tariff within the quota	Tariff over quota
1	1507 10 00	Raw soybean oil	0%	45%
2	1507 90 10	Soybean edible oil	17,5%	45%
3	1511 10 00	Raw palm oil	0 %	100%
4	1511 90	Refined palm oil and any palm oil	17,5%	100%
5	1512 11 10	Unrefined sunflower oil	0%	100%
6	1512 19 10	edible sunflower oil	17,5%	100%

Source: compiled by the authors based on data [23] [25]

Preferential duty rates apply to imports originating in countries or territories that have concluded trade agreements with India or from LDCs. India counts 24 countries among the LDCs, including Madagascar, Ethiopia, Burkina Faso, and others [26].

Below are India's current trade agreements [27].

Table 3

India's trade agreements

Agreement	Type	Coverage	Signing an agreement (for goods / services / investments)	Entry into force (agreements on goods / services)	Commitment implementation period
Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam, and India	FTA	Goods, services, investments	1994	1994	1994
India and the Gulf Cooperation Council	FTA	Goods and services	2004	2006г./2008 г.	Negotiations are ongoing
India and Singapore	FTA	Goods, services, investments	2005	2005	2005
India and ASEAN	FTA (2 agreements)	Goods and services	2010	Negotiations are ongoing	2015

Source: compiled by the authors on the basis of data [27]

India and the EAEU: trade relations

India is an important trading partner of the EAEU with further expansion potential. Thus, in 2021, the mutual trade turnover between India and the EAEU countries reached 16.345 billion US dollars. At the same time, the total indicator of exports amounted to 11.3 billion dollars, and imports - 5.1 billion dollars [14]. According to EEC data, India ranks third among EAEU

trading partners in terms of the correspondence of India's export structure to the structure of imports from EAEU countries, and India ranks 12th in terms of the correspondence of its import structure to the structure of exports from EAEU. This indicates that the Indian market today is extremely attractive for the EAEU member states as a whole.

According to EAEC statistical data, the key sectoral areas in the structure of EAEC exports to India in

2021 were textiles and textile products (\$10 million), leather goods (\$4 million), timber, paper and paper products (\$255 million), and mineral products (\$376 million). The main exports to the ECE statistics were textiles (\$10 million), leather goods (\$4 million), wood, paper and paper products (\$255 million), mineral products (\$376 million), electrical machinery (\$698 million), railway locomotives or tramway cars, rolling stock and parts (\$11 million), chemical products (\$183 million) and other products (\$183 million). The main areas of EAEU imports from India in the mentioned period are fish and crustaceans, molluscs and other aquatic species (USD 156 million), vegetables and some edible root and tuber crops (USD 41 million), edible fruits [fruits] and nuts (USD 45 million), Coffee, tea, mate [Paraguayan tea] and spices (USD 143 million), cereals (USD 76 million), oil seeds and fruits (USD 112 million), products of processing of vegetables [fruits], nuts or other plant parts (USD 30 million). Cereals (\$76 million), oilseeds and fruits (\$112 million), processed vegetables, fruits [fruits], nuts or other plant parts (\$30 million), chemical products (\$915 million), cotton, textile fibers, knitwear (\$97 million), metals (\$371 million), electrical machinery and equipment (\$698 million), etc.[28].

Conclusions

Analysis of WTO statistics shows that the average applied MFN tariff of EAEU member states does not exceed 6.7%, while India increased its average MFN tariff from 13.4% to 18.3% over the period under review. India's weighted average rates are also at a high level, with a calculated value of 12.6% for India (63.3% for agricultural goods and 9.4% for industrial goods). In addition, India actively applies non-tariff regulation measures, primarily anti-dumping, as well as sanitary and phytosanitary measures. Obviously, the conclusion of an FTA is a comprehensive and effective mechanism for reducing trade restrictions. Taking into account these data and the analysis carried out above, it can be noted that the potential for the development of trade and economic relations between the EAEU and India is great, especially at this stage of development, when sanctions are applied against Russia. This means that there is an opportunity to occupy those niches that were blocked by the application of sanctions and to enter the markets of friendly countries, one of the most important among which is India. Taking into account the analysis conducted, it seems reasonable to focus on reducing tariffs on the following goods (those with the highest rates and those of interest for supplies from the EAEU):

- Animal products (average applied rate - 32.5%);
- Dairy products (35.7%);
- Fruit and vegetables (33.6%);
- Cereals (37.3%);
- Oilseeds (53.4%);
- Mineral products and metals (11.8%);
- Chemical products (10.3%).

There is also a need for infrastructure development and the introduction of digital systems along the length of delivery, such as the introduction of a single window system and the introduction of volute transactions in cryptocurrencies only in foreign trade relations.

References

1. Order of the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Russian Federation of 19.04.2022 No. 1532/list of goods for which parallel import is allowed - <http://publication.pravo.gov.ru/Document/View/0001202205060001?index=1> ;
2. COVID-19 induced lockdown effect on wheat supply chain and prices in India – Insights from state interventions led resilience (AG Adeeth Cariappa, Kamlesh Kumar Acharya, Chaitanya Ashok Adhav, Sendhil R, P. Ramasundaram, Anuj Kumar, Satyavir Singh, Gyanendra Pratap Singh)//Socio-Economic Planning Sciences/Volume 84, December 2022//<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2022.101366>;
3. Price analysis and forecasting for decision making: Insights from wheat markets in India (Cariappa, A.G.A., Kathayat, B., Karthiga, S., Sendhil, R.)//Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences/Volume 90, Issue 5, 2020, Pages 979-984/;
4. Competitive pricing of substitute products under supply disruption (Varun Gupta, Dmitry Ivanov, Tsan-Ming Choi)//Omega/Volume 101, June 2021//<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2020.102279> ;
5. Urban Food Markets and the Lockdown in India (Narayanan Sudha, Saha Shree)//May 12, 2020/ Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3599102> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3599102>;
6. Preferential trade agreements and MFN tariffs: Global evidence (David J. Kuenzel, Rishi R. Sharma)// European Economic Review/ Volume 138, September 2021/ DOI- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurocorev.2021.103850>;
7. Exploring the 'non-tariff measures black box': Whose regulatory NTMs on which products improve the imported quality? (Mahdi Ghodsi)//International Economics/Volume 173, May 2023/DOI- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inteco.2022.11.007>;
8. Intra-bloc tariffs and preferential margins in trade agreements (Emanuel Ornelas, Patricia Tovar)// Journal of International Economics/Volume 138, September 2022/ DOI - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2022.103643>;
9. Characterising non-tariff trade policy (Julia Grüber, Oliver Reiter)// Economic Analysis and Policy/Volume 71, September 2021, Pages 138-163/ DOI - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2021.04.007>;
10. Preferential trade agreements and MFN tariffs: Global evidence (David J. Kuenzel, Rishi R. Sharma)//European Economic Review/ Volume 138, September 2021/DOI - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurocorev.2021.103850>;
11. Reducing tariff evasion: The role of trade facilitation (Cosimo Beverelli, Rohit Ticku)//Journal of Comparative Economics/Volume 50, Issue 2, June 2022, Pages 534-554/ DOI - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jce.2021.12.004>;
12. Decision No. 14 "On the start of negotiations with the Republic of India on a free trade zone." URL: <https://docs.eaeunion.org/docs/ru-ru/01415502/>;
13. Republic of India // Eurasian Economic Commission. URL: <https://eec.eaeunion.org/comission/departament/dotp/torgovye-soglasheniya/india.php>;

14. Foreign trade with third countries // Eurasian Economic Commission. URL: https://eec.eaeunion.org/upload/files/dep_stat/tradestat/tables/extra/2021_180/E202112_2_1.pdf;

15. Foreign trade with third countries//Statistical tables//Eurasian Economic Commission [Electronic resource] Access mode: https://eec.eaeunion.org/comission/departement/dep_stat/tradestat/tables/extra/;

16. THE CUSTOMS TARIFF ACT, 1975 (51 Of 1975) [Electronic resource]. // Central board of indirect taxes and customs: [website]. - Access mode: <https://www.cbic.gov.in/resources/htdocs-cbec/customs/cst2021-301221/General%20Notes.pdf> ;

17. Make in India\ Sectors [Electronic resource]. // Make in India: [website]. - Access mode: <https://www.makeinindia.com/sectors> ;

18. World Tariff Profiles [Electronic resource]. // WTO iLibrary : [website]. - Access mode: <https://www.wto-ilibrary.org/content/series/25193147>;

19. T HE SECOND SCHEDULE - EXPORT TARIFF [Electronic resource]. // Central board of Indirect Taxes and Customs/ Department of revenue/ Ministry of finance/ Government of India: [website]. - Access mode: <https://www.cbic.gov.in/resources/htdocs-cbec/customs/cst2022-200422/The%20Second%20Schedule-Export%20Tariff.pdf;jsessionid=DB2C96BBDCE96EEFF80C6A8C80DF4CD5> ;

20. TRADE POLICY REVIEW\REPORT BY THE SECRETARIAT\INDIA [Electronic resource]. // World Trade Organization: [website]. - Access mode: https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tpr_e/s403_e.pdf ;

21. Tariffs and imports: Summary and duty ranges \India [Electronic resource]. // World Trade Organization: [website]. - Access mode: https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/statis_e/daily_update_e/tariff_profiles/IN_e.pdf ;

22. Tariffs and imports: Summary and duty ranges\India [Electronic resource]. // World Trade Organization: [website]. - Access mode: https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/statis_e/daily_update_e/tariff_profiles/IN_E.pdf ;

23. Notification No. 48/2021-Customs [Electronic resource]. // Central board of indirect taxes and customs\ Department of Revenue\ Ministry of Finance\ Government of India: [website]. - Access Mode: <https://www.cbic.gov.in/resources/htdocs-cbec/customs/cs-act/notifications/notfns-2021/cs-tarr2021/cs48-2021.pdf> ;

24. Notification No. 30/2022-Customs [Electronic resource]. // Central board of indirect taxes and customs\ Department of Revenue\ Ministry of Finance\ Government of India: [website]. - Access mode: <https://www.cbic.gov.in/resources/htdocs-cbec/customs/cs-act/notifications/notfns-2022/cs-tarr2022/cs30-2022.pdf;jsessionid=C38E733C7B544EAAF70CC1B51921DE92> ;

25. CUSTOMS TARIFF OF INDIA 2022 [Electronic resource]. // Central board of indirect taxes and customs\ Department of Revenue\ Ministry of Finance\ Government of India: [website]. - Access mode: [https://www.cbic.gov.in/resources/htdocs-cbec/customs/cst2022-010522/customs-tariff-\(chapter-1%20to%2098\)-01-05-2022-updated-27072022.pdf;jsessionid=6C462219BBBEA4EC086449D9BE7E8980](https://www.cbic.gov.in/resources/htdocs-cbec/customs/cst2022-010522/customs-tariff-(chapter-1%20to%2098)-01-05-2022-updated-27072022.pdf;jsessionid=6C462219BBBEA4EC086449D9BE7E8980) ;

26. Least Developed Countries [Electronic resource]. // Indian trade portal: [website]. - Access mode: <https://www.indiantradeportal.in/vs.jsp?lang=0&id=0,25,45,539,1496> ;

27. Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN) and India Free Trade Agreement (FTA) negotiations [Electronic resource]. // Government of India/Ministry of Commerce and Industry/ Department of commerce: [website]. - Mode of access: <https://commerce.gov.in/international-trade-trade-agreements-indias-current-engagements-in-rtas/association-of-south-east-asian-nations-asean-and-india-free-trade-agreement-fta-negotiations/> ;

28. Statistical tables//Foreign trade with third countries//January - December 2021//Eurasian Economic Commission [electronic resource]: access mode - https://eec.eaeunion.org/comission/departement/dep_stat/tradestat/tables/extra/2021.php .